

THE POSSIBILITIES OF INTEGRATIVE-MODULAR EDUCATION IN THE SCHOOL OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *This article considers the implementation of integration under the condition of the organization of interdisciplinary and interdisciplinary courses and programs based on the principles of development and modular training. Integration is aimed at the formation of a qualitatively new type of generalized, "end-to-end" knowledge, which simultaneously acts as a method of knowledge and cognition.*

Keywords: *integrative and modular training, system knowledge, modular program, education for sustainable development.*

The organization of interdisciplinary or interdisciplinary content of the learning process in the form of training modules with a focus on the formation of students' "end-to-end knowledge" will contribute to the formation of a holistic picture of the world and a holistic worldview. The fundamental importance of the formation of a special type of thinking based on generalized, general scientific knowledge is connected not only with the intensification and humanization of the learning process, but also with the social order of modern society itself, the reorientation of education to solve the problems of sustainable development. Let us list the main requirements imposed on modern man and conditioned by the solution of the tasks of sustainable development of society.

1. The society of sustainable development requires from a modern person the development of such personal qualities as mobility, dynamism, constructiveness, adaptability, functional literacy.

2. The current situation on the labor market in modern society, when a person radically changes the sphere of professional activity every 10-15 years, imposes the requirement of universal professionalism — the ability to change spheres and methods of activity based on knowledge management skills [6].

3. The phenomena of globalization and integration in various spheres of life require a transition from the concept of a "good specialist" to the concept of a "good employee" who can work in a team, can make independent decisions, take initiative, manage himself, capable of innovation.

4. Informatization and globalization dictate the requirement of proficiency in the means and language of global communication (modern means of communication — the Internet, e-mail), and among foreign languages, English is distinguished by the level of globality.

5. Internationalization and integration of various spheres of social activity presupposes successful and effective intercultural communication, knowledge of social codes of representatives of other communities and spheres of activity.

6. The development of the economy, the commercialization of various spheres of public life presupposes that a modern successful person has a certain mindset, economic and environmental thinking, developed "business enterprise", "entrepreneurial spirit".

Achievement of the indicated result is possible, in our opinion, provided the organization of interdisciplinary (at school) or interdisciplinary (at university) content (which in its essence should be general scientific, end-to-end knowledge, organized at the level of leading content ideas). Interdisciplinary (interdisciplinary) integration of content is organized in the form of training modules. The question arises: what subjects or disciplines can we talk about integrating?

For example, we consider it possible to establish interdisciplinary relationships between general education courses at school: economics, ecology, economic geography, computer science, English. Or combine it into a training module at a university (direction "psychological and pedagogical education") "Modern educational technologies", such disciplines as "Active teaching methods in psychological and pedagogical activity", "Computer technologies in education", "Foreign languages in the field of professional communication". The need to integrate academic disciplines into modular programs becomes, at the present stage of society's development, a fundamental condition for the success of both the personality of a student — a future student, and the personality of a student — a future specialist who is aware of his role in creating a sustainable development society. Thus, there is a need to develop the didactic competence of a university teacher and a teacher [7].

In conclusion, we note that integrative-modular training can contribute not only to improving the effectiveness of the learning process and its developmental impact, reducing the learning load, but also to the formation of a certain type of universal knowledge in the student-a method that determines the type of general scientific thinking, and ultimately contributes to the formation of a successful personality of a sustainable development society, easily adaptable to rapidly changing environmental conditions, effectively operating in the global world community and having its holistic picture in its mind.

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